

ISic0405

I.Sicily inscription 0405

Language

Latin

Type

building

Material

marble (white)

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

Lost?

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

'rep. extra moenia in vinea Barth.'

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Lost

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Neratius Palmatus v(ir) [c(larissimus)cons(ularis)]

2. etiam frontem scaenae O[---]

Apparatus

Text of CIL

Translation

Commentary

Suggested to commemorate the decoration of the frons scenae of the Syracuse theatre at the expense of the consularis Neratius Palmatus.

Digital identifiers:

TM 491616

EDCS 21900446

Bibliography

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